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ASYMMETRY IN THE PROCESS OF FORMING AND REALISING HUMAN CAPITAL, AND WAYS OF OVERCOMING IT*

Keywords: *Human capital, asymmetry, investment, secondary vocational education, spillover effect.*

Ключевые слова: *человеческий капитал, асимметрия, инвестиции, среднее профессиональное образование, эффект перелива.*

Расширенная аннотация на русском языке

Статья посвящена проблеме асимметрии, которая складывается в процессе формирования и реализации человеческого капитала. Данная проблема приобретает особую значимость, поскольку в современных условиях человеческий капитал все в большей степени выступает как наиболее креативный и эффективный фактор социально-экономического развития. В связи с этим возрастает значимость экономической оценки человеческого капитала – в первую очередь, для выявления наиболее оптимальных параметров его формирования и эффективных способов реализации. В этом контексте расходы на формирование человеческого капитала в сферах образования, здравоохранения и культуры выступают в качестве

инвестиций и должны быть соотнесены с их отдачей. Возникающая при этом асимметрия может иметь разные формы проявления, в том числе такие, как положительная и отрицательная, внешняя и внутренняя асимметрия. Преобладание положительной асимметрии является важным фактором для экономического развития той или иной страны. В статье отражен как международный опыт формирования человеческого капитала, так и ряд его характеристик в Азербайджанской Республике. Особое внимание обращено роли образования в процессе формирования человеческого капитала. Инвестиции в образовательную сферу отмечаются как наиболее значимые в силу того, что именно они формируют до 60 % человеческого капитала. Отражена динамика индекса человеческого капитала в Азербайджане

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*JEL codes: E22, E24, J24.

* **Citation:** Nazrin Rustambayova (2021). Asymmetry in the Process of Formation and Realization of Human Capital and Ways to Overcome it. *Problems in Political Economy*, 1 (25): 184-196.

* **Цитирование:** Рустамбекова Н. (2021). Асимметрия при формировании и реализации человеческого капитала и пути ее преодоления // *Вопросы политической экономики*. №1 (25). С. 184-196.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4666471 (<https://zenodo.org/record/4666471>)

не, а также факторы, воздействующие на него, в том числе продолжительность жизни, ожидаемое количество лет обучения, среднее количество лет обучения. Также представлена стратегия развития человеческого капитала в Азербайджанской Республике, где ведущее значение придается его конкурентоспособности. Одновременно актуализируются и вопросы асимметрии между формированием и эффективным задействованием человеческого капитала на личностном, корпоративном и макроэкономическом уровнях. Достижение положительной асимметрии между расходами на человеческий капитал и доходами работников, прибылью предприятий, ростом ВВП выдвигается в статье в императив реализации национальных экономических интересов. Значительное внимание уделяется в статье международному опыту формирования и реализации человеческого капитала на корпоративном уровне. В качестве наглядного примера отмечена практика японской компании Тойота с ее потоком создания ценности сотрудников, повышенным вниманием к квалификации персонала и профессиональному обучению. Автором был проведен опрос с целью показать основные причины внешней асимметрии в Азербайджане и найти пути ее преодоления. Респондентами опроса стали граждане страны, проживающие за рубежом. Опрос был проведен с целью выявления основных причин миграции из страны, которая приводит к внешней асимметрии человеческого капитала. В статье анализируются также факторы внутренней асимметрии в формировании и реализации человеческого капитала. Они выявляют, в частности, реальную величину доходов на всех хозяйственных уровнях, оставшуюся после возмещения затрат, включая налоги. При этом выдвигается

формула соотношения между добавленной стоимостью и человеческим капиталом. На макроэкономическом уровне она выглядит следующим образом: если разделить стоимость валовой добавленной стоимости на уровень занятости в стране, то мы получим и стоимость национального человеческого капитала.

Не только в Азербайджане, но и во многих постсоветских странах, асимметрия между формированием и реализацией человеческого капитала связано с наличием неиспользованного человеческого капитала. Безусловно, это весомая причина асимметрии между расходами на формирование и результатами реализации человеческого капитала. По нашим подсчетам, до 18 % выпускников Высших Учебных Заведений не работают по своей специальности, что приводит к значительным потерям в расходах на их образование, которые приходится покрывать либо государству, либо самому частному лицу – таким образом, человек теряет свое время и деньги. Это разновидность внутренней асимметрии в формировании и реализации человеческого капитала, когда государство предоставляет общественные блага населению, часто бесплатно, но они не используются по назначению. Этот момент иногда характеризуют как результат иррационального поведения. Однако он, на наш взгляд, в значительной степени связан с асимметрией между структурой подготавливаемых специалистов и реальными потребностями в кадрах на рынке труда. По существу, это институциональная асимметрия, которая порождает необходимость коррекции между институтами формирования и реализации человеческого капитала в целях устойчивого воспроизводства совокупного общественного продукта.

Introduction

The human capital in the modern world performs as the most effective and creative factor of socio-economic development. In this regard the importance of human capital's economic evaluation increases – firstly, in order to identify the most optimal parameters of its formation and effective ways of its realization. In this context one of the key problems is to determine the asymmetry of spending on the human capital and its return as a result of application of the education, health and cultural values that is within the individual.

The positive asymmetry at which the prosperity of a society and the incomes on all the levels of economy exceed the spending on human capital accumulation becomes principally important for any country's economic growth and competitive advantages achievement. This requires a careful consideration of human capital phenomenon, which is important not only on individual, but also on corporate and nationwide scales. It is about the rationalization of a mechanism of human capital formation with its maximal return to achieve an economic development. This problem becomes even more important all over the world, with its own specific way of solution in each country.

In spite of the fact, that many publications on the phenomenon of human capital exist nowadays, not all the issues solved on a theoretical level. In particular, the balance (symmetry and asymmetry) of spending and returns in the process of human capital formation and realization remains absolutely not researched, although the "capital" interpretation of this problem shows the obviousness of this statement both in a theoretical and empirical sense.

1. The importance of education in formation of human capital

Fostering of human capital in Azerbaijan acts as a leading socio-economic development path of the country. A human capital issue brought to the fore in all the strategic programs and projects, implementation of which carries the national economy forward to the higher levels of technological progress and a population's prosperity. That is a calibrated policy, which answers the global challenges, as the balances of power in the world economy nowadays. It shows that the most developed countries are those that carry out the investments in the effective realization of human capital. At the same time, the human capital as a factor of production includes a wide set of a people's qualities. For instance, L. Thurow considers that "human capital includes such qualities of a man as the dignity of a political and social stability, which is achieved mainly as a result of a relevant upbringing and education" (Thurow, 1997).

It is quite important moment because a formation and realization of human capital occurs over a long period and covers the generations of people; their aspirations and values can provide a high efficiency in the paradigm of foreseeing the future demands of both an individual and a society.

Taking into consideration the fact that education is a structural core of a human capital, which accounts for 60% of its accumulative share, investments in this sphere directly influence Azerbaijan's positions in the international ratings. In the Human Capital Index proposed by the World Bank in 2018, Azerbaijan takes the 69th position¹.

The results of research of the World Bank experts on the indicators

¹ <http://databank.worldbank.org>

Table 1.
Dynamics of Human Capital Index and factors affecting it in Azerbaijan

	Life Expectancy	Expected Years of Schooling	Mean Years of Schooling	GNI per capita	Human Development Index
1995	65.3	10.0	10.2	3,387	0.612
2000	66.8	10.4	10.6	4,314	0.640
2005	68.8	10.7	10.7	6,940	0.679
2010	71.0	11.7	10.7	15,246	0.740
2015	71.9	12.7	10.7	16,334	0.758
2016	72.0	12.7	10.7	15,751	0.757
2017	72.1	12.7	10.7	15,600	0.757

Source: www.stat.gov.az

of the human capital's fostering in Azerbaijan are as follows: the child born in the country today would be 60 % more productive if, besides possessing physical integrity he or she would get a decent education. The value of a Human Capital Index increased from 0.56 to 0.60 during 2012-2017 years. Additionally, as it stated in the World Bank report, the indicator of human capital for Azerbaijan is slightly higher than the average for its income group¹. Here it means that Azerbaijan, being a country of a higher-middle income, has the Index value higher than the average for its group of countries, which, of course, is encouraging.

Another, an equally important index is a Human Development Index– was designed by UNDP and also reflects a real situation with the human capital in the country. Let's compare its dynamics, the dynamics of the Index components, and the Gross National Income per capita in Azerbaijan during the period from 1995 till 2017.

The phenomenon of a fee-based education is the subject to a specific highlight. The point is that such fees are not always affordable to the households, which often leads to the refusal and

an interruption of the education and consequently can be interpreted as the losses in the human capital.

Meanwhile, the relative weight both of students and graduates of the secondary vocational education that get a fee-based education increases; respectfully, the amount of those receive the scholarships decreases (see Figure 1 and Figure 2).

In order to tackle such a situation, the government and the educational institutions apply different benefits to certain population categories, including exemption or postponement from educational payments. One of effective ways is the "student-bank" system – the lending of education, where the interest rates are still too high. One of the most attractive is a loan fund for students – "Maarifchi", which renders aid in getting the education by the students of underprivileged families. The standard loan has a 5-year period of repayment and an 8% interest rate. After student finishes the education, he or she has a one-year preferential period until the beginning of repayment of a debt that includes the loan and an interest. A student can take a loan up to 2 373 USD annually with the maximum overall loan of 11 869 USD per one student.

¹ <http://hdr.undp.org>

Figure 1. The relative weight of scholarship receivers in higher educational institutions.

Source: <https://www.stat.gov.az/source/education/>

Figure 2. The relative weight of scholarship receivers in secondary vocational educational institutions.

Source: <https://www.stat.gov.az/source/education/>

After the two sessions of applications' submitting took place, the pilot program MSLF (Maarifchi Student Loan Fund) has signed the student's loan contracts with

90 students from 14 universities for a total amount of 108 710 USD¹.

¹ <http://blogs.worldbank.org>

Human capital is the differentiator for organizations and the actual basis for competitive advantage (Chatzkel, 2004). It is important to take into consideration high economic effect of the investments in the personnel's development by the business-structures in the international practice. For example, the researches that were carried out in 3200 American companies by the Pennsylvania State University specialists (USA) showed that a 10 % increase in the expenditure on the personnel training give the increase in the labor productivity of 8.5 %. The same increase of the capital investments in the physical (material) factors of production gives only a 3.8 % increase of productivity. For instance, in 2004 after the assessing the effectiveness of training courses in Motorola company, it was revealed that every single dollar investment in training had brought 33 dollars back as the profit (Akbar and other, 2008. Pp. 26-38).

The problem of asymmetry in spending and returns to human capital exists at the corporate level too. It can be solved by creating a system of incentives, both tangible and intangible. The best example of the relationship between a firm and an employee, as well as the loyalty of the latter, are Japanese firms, in particular Toyota Motor Company, where from the very beginning of its activities, investment in human capital was the key to success (Liker, 2004).

The founder of the Toyota Motor Company, Kiyotiro Toeda, said that if people were brought together, each of whom would fulfill their duties to the maximum, their capabilities would grow not in arithmetic, but in geometrical progression.

The main activity of leaders of Toyota is personnel training. There is also a remuneration of staff, more often

a team working together or the entire staff, when the company succeeds. This done in order for the staff to feel their involvement in the success of the company, as well as for the formation of a collective spirit.

Toyota's corporate culture's distinction, as well as most Japanese firms, is team commitment or so-called collectivism, which not found in Western, American firms, where preference given to individualism.

Due to that collectivism, as well as employee loyalty to an employer in Japan, there is no problem of frictional unemployment, since employees are not inclined to change their workplace, and therefore there is no problem of asymmetry of costs and results in the formation and implementation of human capital at the corporate level.

Asymmetry at the corporate level, as well as external asymmetry, has a positive and negative effect on the host and losing firms, respectively. However, it is worth considering the effect of this asymmetry on an individual who decides to change jobs, in most cases to improve working conditions, get higher wages and other factors that undoubtedly have a positive effect on their productivity and positively affect their livelihoods.

While investing in individuals firms do not have any guarantee about returns unlike investing in machines. Individuals can always decide to go absent or work badly. The theory of human capital states than an individual will invest in human capital up to the point at which the marginal return equal to the marginal cost (Elliot, 1991).

Asymmetry in formation of human capital can have an institutional aspect, which, for example, means the unequal distribution of students in universities and secondary vocational education institutes.

1.2. Secondary vocational education as a way to decrease asymmetry of human capital

Development of secondary vocational education and enhancing the prestige of labor occupations is one of the prioritized strategies for Azerbaijan in the medium term. It is expected that 450 thousand working places would be created in Azerbaijan by the 2025th year. These are new enterprises that would be state-funded, private business-funded, or on a base of foreign investments that form the demand on the skilled workforce. In the end, all these measures would find their reflection not only in GDP of the country, individual or corporate incomes (not that significant), but in such a key indicator as the value added. The value added – it is the sum of money that is created by the human mind and labor which explicitly expresses the productivity of human capital. In this sense the gross value added acts as a formed (created) value, as it shows the difference between the sum of material goods produced and the sum of the underused resources. A Stern Stewart and Co. organization has popularized the term “economic value added” (EVA) which is equivalent to the human value added (Stern Stewart, 2002).

Economic Value Added = Net operating profit after taxes – (costs of capital * capital).

The disadvantage of EVA is in complication of its calculation and that is why it is not widely used (Murphy, 2007).

It shows the real income value left not only after repayment of all the costs, including the taxes, but also after segregation of the value of the invested capital. Connection between the value added and human capital is as follows: if we divide the value of gross

value added on the employment level in the country, we will obtain the human capital value that we need.

The industry of a soviet period in Azerbaijan that was subjected to destruction has left lots of unemployed workers, enough skilled ones but not always suitable for the structure and a quality of a modern production process. Training and retraining of a qualified workforce and primary chain specialists is an unalienable part of an educational system of a country and one of major components of the maintenance of a sustainable and effective fostering of a human capital, the non-oil industry and an entire state’s socio-economic development”. 40-60% of general secondary education graduates in the developed countries enter precisely the primary vocational educational institutions while in Azerbaijan this value constitutes less than 11% which shows a low interest of the population to this system. In this case, an asymmetry presents, because the number of specialists with a higher education is three times higher than the number of secondary vocational education graduates – 163.8 thousand students studied in higher educational institutions in Azerbaijan in the period 2017-2018; what about the secondary vocational educational institutions, this number reached 51.7 thousand only.

Emphasizing this moment has a high empirical importance in the law “On vocational education” adopted by the Azerbaijan Republic’s Parliament (National Assembly) in April, 2018 by which several benefits in financial, legal and other fields are set out in order to encourage the employers of a primary vocational education which would create opportunities for the private sector to show a higher interest

Figure 3. Number of students studying in secondary vocational educational institutions.

Source: State Statistical Committee of Azerbaijan Republic

for the partnership with the vocational education¹. However, an integration of employers into the system of vocational education and teaching, their enrollment into the process of specialized mid-level personnel is chosen as one of the main directions of building relationships of a close cooperation between the employers and the vocational educational institutions. A significant headway has to be implemented in Azerbaijan, as, according to the state Strategy on development of education in the Azerbaijan Republic, “an enrolling of employers into the education process and the personnel’s training, and also into the modernization of the essence of education remains on an extremely low level. The employers have to be able to participate in the process of a personnel’s training to advance conditions related to the personnel trained and, respectfully, to realize their own responsibility.

Quite an extraordinary project was suggested in the Training Center on a vocational preparation that is planned to operate on a base of Korean educational standards involving Baku state vocational education center in the sector of industry and innovations. Under the project, the new center will feature the advanced resources and infrastructure and offer education and training in eight occupations: mechanics, electronics, electrical engineering, industrial installation, construction, information technologies, automobile and automation. The center will be created using the Korean curriculum and with involvement of Korean specialists². A significance of such educational institutions’ founding lies in the fact that they may foster overcoming not only the unemployment but also an implicit labor market. The most significant volume of implicit unemployment presents in the construction sector, maintenance

¹ <https://cabmin.gov.az>

² <https://edu.gov.az>

works, tutoring, private recruiting of housekeepers, the restaurants' services.

To comprehend the importance of a vocational training on the educational level it is of a peculiar interest to mention China's experience. A vocational-technical education is that special form of education, which is aimed at getting a specific knowledge and skills. It is more flexible, adaptable to the demands of economic development and plays an important role in the economic growth; that is why it takes a central position in the educational system of China. This sphere of education in PRC today regulated by the Vocational education Law of the PRC, which influences: the economic development; employment level – 95 % of graduates have a permanent job; social equality – 90 % of students get the aid from the government. Moreover, the low-income families and those who enrolled into the agriculture are exempted from the education payment; the regions' development – about 60 % of graduates work in different parts of the country.

The development of a secondary vocational education field is contextualized within the China's model of economic development, in which, according to the PRC general secretary Xi Jinping, "China follows a people-oriented development philosophy and is committed to bettering the lives of its people. Development is of the people, by the people and for the people (H.E. Xi Jinping, 2017).

Distant training is widely disseminated and oriented on the mid-level professional contingent and provision of them with jobs on the ground. China's experience – a country that achieved a tremendous success in the accelerated development of

its economy, needed to take into the consideration in the process of modernization of a secondary vocational education in relation to our country.

2. Types of asymmetry in process of formation of human capital

Besides the process of formation of human capital, its realization is also important – by pursuing the occupation. An untapped human capital wastes its fundamental essence in fact; and in the modern world of developing technologies this aspect is even more evident. Certainly, this is a significant reason of an asymmetry between the spending on formation and the results of human capital's realization. Up to 18% of higher educational institutions' graduates do not pursue their own occupation, which leads to significant losses in the costs on their education that either the government or the individual has to cover – so, an individual lost his or her time and money on the educational resource, which was not used. This is type of internal asymmetry in formation and realization of human capital. Internal asymmetry while formation and implementation of human capital can be compared to the "free-rider" problem – or the "free-rider" effect. It is connected with providing the public goods to the population by the government, often free of charge, when the abovementioned free rider uses the goods as everyone else, not paying for them or spending just a little sum of money (Oliver, Walker, 1984. Pp. 3-24). This moment acts as a result of irrational behavior.

The positive asymmetry is observed also among the employment of a female, the decrease of unemployment is traced; if the female unemployment rate in Azerbaijan was on the level

of 12.8 % in 2000, this indicator has declined to 6.1 % in 2018. (The Global economy, 2018).

As in many other countries, the so-called “external asymmetry” between the formation and implementation of human capital exists in Azerbaijan. The external asymmetry, which is connected with the migration of mainly high-qualified human capital from the country, was quite high in the early 1990s after the state gained independence and the “brain drain” became a problem, which touched almost all the post-soviet republics, and is still taking place nowadays. Many developed countries, attract qualified staff today, the so-called “brain-poach” negatively influences the further development of a country from which the personnel migrates. According to the statistics, migration in Azerbaijan has dropped 10 times since 1990. Nevertheless, the brain drain problem, high-qualified personnel’s and student’s migration problems are still on the agenda in Azerbaijan. To determine the main reasons of the migration and the circumstances that may bring the migrants back into the homeland, a survey among the Azerbaijanis living abroad was carried out. The survey’s results showed that the following circumstances might bring the migrants back into Azerbaijan: work in given specialization (7 %), favorable working conditions (15 %), high level of social protection (18 %), acceptable fees (22 %), gender equality at work (2 %), career opportunities (21 %) and other factors (15 %).

An analysis of the abovementioned circumstances would prevent the “brain drain” in the future. However, besides the economic, there are moral and ethical aspects of the emigration problem, especially among the

young specialists – Azerbaijan higher educational institutions’ graduates. It is about a social quality of people which is referred to as “the degree of participation of citizens in a social and economic life of a society, in which their prosperity and an individual potential enhances”.

The socialization is “a process of acquiring by an individual of social norms, cultural values, and the templates of behavior of the society he or she belongs to”. All these moments of socialization are preliminary inculcated into the person in a family, which is a primary element that sets the most important preconditions of a human capital’s formation. An absolute majority of people in the very beginning of their lives (until they reach a 5-year-old age) are brought up in the family and pre-school institutions, where their character is shaped, their introduction to the traditions, moral values takes place. A systematic evaluation of an early childhood intervention designed to improve a variety of children’s skills—including delaying gratification—revealed dramatic benefits for later life outcomes including educational attainment (Heckman and other, 2010).

Henceforth the external circumstances suggest a wide range of socio-economic conditions for a individual’s development. In this case it is of high importance that the parameters of social behavior and conceiving the world that were internalized in the childhood and gained in the adulthood complement each other. Only in this paradigm of formation and fostering human capital can be considered as a national wealth and can enhance it. This period is quite significant by the essence, because the basic functions of the brain start shaping before the

children are born, and this process lasts till they reach 5 years. At this time the brain's ability to be trained particular skills is the highest; it decreases with the age. If miss this opportunity, the child might find it hard to study and harness new skills. The researches show that each additional dollar invested in increasing the quality of nutrition and a level of pre-school programs would bring into the national economy from 6 to 17 dollars in the future. That is why the investments during the first years of a child's life are the most economically effective capital investments that made by the government¹.

Conclusion

After carrying out a study in the country, the author suggests the following strategy of development.

Firstly, an expansion and a diversification of the sources of financing in the educational system is required to reach a maximal correlation between the gross national income and a human capital; here budget transfers take the prevailing position. This step might help to overcome an intra-institutional asymmetry, as there are a number of asymmetric patterns both in institutional and investing aspects of human capital's fostering in Azerbaijan.

Secondly, an assistance of the business entities for the students both of vocational and higher educational institutions to let the latter get loans on education might become a highly effective step. The corporate investment into the educational component of human capital may take different forms: an investment into students of a profile higher educational institutions via providing scholarships, grants that can be nominated by the enterprises

to cover the costs on education with the employment contract provided; an investment into the corporation's employees via providing the opportunities to get a second higher education, postgraduate education, courses on skills development; founding of private educational centers, research centers that can be implemented in collaboration with the profile higher educational institutions. It is very important to provide students the conditions to demonstrate their abilities, to involve them into trainings and the internship in their companies. Joining such projects by the entrepreneurs is of a high importance especially in relation to the secondary educational institutions due to the fact that namely they require highly-trained personnel possessing not only the higher education but also the representatives of a vocational education to satisfy the needs of a developing industry of a new technological level. The main thing is to create the environment for the youth to have the confidence in the fact that they would be able to get a high-quality education and pursue their occupation.

Thirdly, there is a sense to enroll "informal" (self-employment) into the legal work via the legal licensing, a system of a vocational training and certification, insurance and pension. Providing them with the tax benefits and other preferences can largely improve the situation on the labor market, broaden the base of an entrepreneurship, provide the consumers' security. In the end, "informal", mainly self-taught, are practically deprived of an opportunity to enter the social "elevators" – the vertical of a career growth.

Fourthly, the formation of highly trained personnel in all the fields of

¹ <http://blogs.worldbank.org>

economy is quite important in our country. During the last years, the field of agriculture has started rapidly developing thanks to the government policy of broadening and developing of non-oil industries. A formation of the qualified personnel in the regions is the key to development of the provincial regions of the country, where the new educational institutions that would satisfy the market demands of their location have to be opened to that end. In this aspect, a tourism industry comes to the fore. For the further expansion and improvement of this field in the qualitative aspect, it is advisable not only to educate on this occupation but also to enroll students and graduates into work in the regions favorable to tourists, which would lead both the reduction of unemployment and improvement of the touristic services. This is the spillover effect while formation and realization of human capital, when the development of one field leads to the positive results in the other fields. This all requires spending, which would, undoubtedly, be profitable on all the levels. In this case, it is again confirmed that the institutional

and financial aspects of human capital's fostering have to be closely correlated without creating asymmetric deviations.

Fifthly, the increase in spending on the research works is the priority to pass to the knowledge-intensive production which is being served by an increasing amount of those who are enrolled into the research development of a fundamental and an applied character.

The further Azerbaijan advances in its development, the higher there would be the demand in the research personnel on the national labor market. The human capital should yield an income, and as higher it is, the more would the craving for the knowledge to be, the higher the requirements of those who study towards the teachers to be, the higher their determination to the innovative methods of education to be, the broader a search for the intellectual resources by the entrepreneurs to take place. As a result not only the government but also the individuals, families, businesses would invest more in human capital.

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